

NANOSTRUCTURAL OXIDE FIBERS FOR COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The developed technology makes it possible to synthesize long and short nanostructured polycrystal oxide fibers with high porosity that are characterized by mesoporosity and a large specific surface. The study performed permitted us to establish the mechanism for formation of fibrous oxide with a complex architecture, including metal oxide nanoparticles, nanopores and microcapillaries.

Based on the calculations of crystallite sizes, it is found that crystallographic transformations of fiber oxides cause substance to disperse. Structural changes in fibrous oxides are followed by varying the porosity nature, pore size and a value of specific surface. The obtained regularities permit us to predict the properties and to control the technology of producing nanostructural fibrous oxide materials.

KEYWORDS: refractory oxide fibres, mechanism of formation, biomimetics, preparation, structure, properties.

INTRODUCTION

Over the last twenty years the development and improvement of the methods of manufacturing and studying nanostructural materials gave birth to the new branch of the materials science – nanotechnology. Synthesis advances made these materials more accessible for study and, in some cases, for production of batches.

For the mass production to be arranged and nanomaterials to be widely used, two important tasks in science and technology must be resolved. The first task suggests that a size of nanostructures must be severely controlled in long operation under variable conditions. The second consists in controlling the thermal and chemical stability of the structures to be obtained. It is known that the less the size of a nanostructure, the easier it is subjected to shift, aggregation, decomposition or other chemical, or thermal actions that can change its shape, composition, and structure. In the production process each material must have a definite range of conditions, over which the assigned characteristics of a material are kept under steady-state operating conditions.

In this connection, of undoubted interest is the synthesis and study of macroobjects composed of homogeneously distributed of nano-sized units. Such structures are formed, resting upon the biomimetics phenomenon when complex architectonics of biological objects is reproduced in inorganic materials [1]. The so-called organic templates are used for

synthesizing inorganic nanostructures. Synthesis of inorganic fibres, with the use of polymer natural, artificial or synthetic fibres and materials as a master matrix is one of the possible ways to produce nanostructural materials.

The aim of the present work was to study the process and mechanism for formation of nanostructured fibres and powders of refractory metal oxides based on alumina, zirconia and another refractory oxides when hydrated cellulose fibres serves as an initial polymer matrix and also to analyze the dependences of their crystalline and porous structure on synthesis conditions and heat treatment temperature.

EXPERIMENT

Ceramic oxide fibres were prepared of hydrated cellulose fibres and tissue by impregnation with aqueous metal salt solutions. Impregnating solutions of aluminium, yttrium, lanthanum, titanium and magnesium chlorides or zirconium oxychloride with a variable ratio of components were used to prepare mono- or polycomponent fibres. In the act of being adsorbed, the solutions were elevated via the capillary channels into the inter fibre space and penetrated first into an amorphous and then in a crystal parts of polysacchride macromolecules [2]. Salt-containing fibres were dried and thermally treated within a special regime from 100 to 1600°C in air.

The processes of forming oxide fibres were studied on the Paulic-Paulic-Erdei thermograph by the differential thermal analysis (DTA). The material was heated in air with a velocity of 5°/min, the weighed portion constituted 0.5 g, and high-pure Al₂O₃ served as a standard substance of comparison. The fibre structure was investigated by the X-ray methods, IR spectroscopy, and scanning electron microscopy. The change in the phase composition of fibre samples thermally by treated at given temperatures was studied by the quantitative X-ray phase analysis. The phase content in these samples was determined through the integral reflex intensities: γ - Al₂O₃ - [400], θ - Al₂O₃ - [200] and [400], α - Al₂O₃ - [012] and [104] MgO - [200] and MgAl₂O₄ - [440], TiO₂ (rutile) - [110] and [101] and anatase - [101] and [200], Y₂O₃ (cubic) - [222] and [400], ZrO₂ monoclinic - [111] and [11 $\bar{1}$], ZrO₂ tetragonal - [111]. A high-pure magnesium oxide powder was used as an external standard. The BET method was adopted to estimate the specific surface and sorption ability of fibrous oxides through adsorption of nitrogen and benzene vapours [3]. Surface microstructure of powders and fibers was examined on the scanning electron microscope (SEM) – JSM-35 (JEOL) with x 10000-15000. A shape and size of particles were examined on the transmission electron microscope (TEM) – JSM 200A with x 100000-120000 and also on the atom-power microscope (APM) - Nanotop 206 (Microtestmachine). Crystallite sizes were determined by the X-ray analysis in terms of the physical broadening of the reflex contours of test phases [4]. Since the oxide fibers were produced without applied pressure, it can be assumed that practically no disclination occurred in crystallite oxides. Hence, the physical broadening of reflexes was mainly caused by their particle size.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hydrated cellulose was chosen as a polymer precursor. Its structure is a complex system composed of microfibrils and micro- and macropores and also of a branched network of microscopic capillaries. Owing to this, cellulose has a large inner surface that plays a determining role in the act of filling capillaries, pores and of absorbing aqueous or organic liquids with polymer molecules. In the impregnating of hydrated cellulose with aqueous solutions of salts, the liquid have filled a capillary space between fibres, pores on the fibre surface and interacted with cellulose macromolecules [5].

According to the thermogravimetric and spectroscopic studies, heating of salt-containing polymer fibres in the oxidizing atmosphere was followed by different chemical processes. First the moisture adsorbed in water was removed (105-110⁰C), and then both the chemically bound water of hydrated cellulose and the crystal water of salts (120-200⁰C). These processes were governed by two endoeffects in the DTA curves. Thermolysis and carbonization of an initial polymer occurred over the temperature range 200-360⁰C. At the same time, above 320⁰C the thermal dissociation of metal salts proceeded, yielding nanoparticles first of hydroxides and then of metal oxides. At the temperatures 450-550⁰C some metal oxides were crystallized (exoeffects in the DTA curves).

Escaping hydrogen chloride was involved in the reaction of cleavage of glycoside bonds of cellulose macromolecules, thus catalyzing the processes of a polymer thermolysis and oxidation of a forming carbon component. These processes were mostly affected by zirconium salt (Fig. 1). Thus, the heating of a salt-containing polymer has resulted in the formation of refractory oxide nanoparticles. Because of high non-compensated surface energy the diffusion processes and mass transfer were developed as a results of which both the contacts were formed between oxide grains, and the linear chain structure was arranged, repeating the architecture of an initial polymer.

Fig. 1: Curves for differential thermal analysis of hydrated cellulose fibres (1), and fibres impregnated with solutions: zirconium oxychloride (2), zirconium oxychloride with addition of yttrium chloride (3) and zirconium oxychloride with addition of yttrium chloride and aluminium chloride (4), versus thermal treatment temperature.

Over the temperature 500-600⁰C the formed alumina particles were X-ray amorphous while the zirconia ones had a tetragonal structure. The additions of yttrium salt to zirconium oxychloride or of chloride titanium and magnesium to aluminium salt were uniformly distributed in the solution and also in the volume of a polymer being impregnated. Heating of such samples of fibres in oxidizing atmosphere has yielded the nanocrystal solid solutions or compounds. If the yttrium and aluminium chloride were added to solution of zirconium oxychloride then the triple solid solution was formed in the salt-containing fibres when they were heated.

The X-ray phase analysis has supported the formation of the cubic phase of alumina at 700⁰C. When the heat treatment temperature of samples was increased up to 900⁰C, the reflexes of the θ -phase were seen on the diffractograms, and at 1100⁰C the γ - and θ -phases of alumina

were transformed into the α -phase of Al_2O_3 , trigonal system with the lattice parameters: $a - 4.74 \text{ \AA}$, $c - 12.94 \text{ \AA}$.

At heating of hydrated aluminium chloride-containing fibres added with magnesium salts, the nanocrystalline alumomagnesium spinel was started to form at $500\text{-}550^\circ\text{C}$. Its content was noticeably increased due to the solid-phase reaction for Al_2MgO_4 formation over the range $1200\text{-}1300^\circ\text{C}$. Parameter of cubic lattice of the low-temperature form was equal to 8.041 \AA and of the high-temperature spinel was equal to 8.080 \AA . Addition of titanium salts to the impregnating solution of aluminium chloride has decelerated alumina crystallization in fibres. Over the range $600\text{-}680^\circ\text{C}$ only titania was crystallized in the anatase phase, and its structural change into rutyl was occurred at $850\text{-}875^\circ\text{C}$, then alumina was crystallized in cubic system. At the impregnation stage, the adding of yttrium salt (3 mol. % in terms of MeO) has partially stabilized the tetragonal structure of zirconia. As a result, the phase ratio in a product was tetragonal: monoclinic = 80 : 20 %.

The produced oxide fibres were composed of nanoparticles. This high-dispersion was responsible for their reactivity when they were sintered and interacted with different powders and liquids. For estimation of oxide grain sizes of fibres we have used the method for determination of the reflex physical broadening of synthesized materials. The analysis of the data obtained has shown that as the annealing temperature of samples was increased, the particle sizes of alumina different phases were varied non-monotonically. So at the beginning of Al_2O_3 crystallization the reflex contours of the γ -phase were broadened and the particle sizes were 4-6 nm. As the temperature was elevated up to $800\text{-}850^\circ\text{C}$, the particle sizes were increased up to 15-17 nm, and the crystallites of the alumina γ -phase were grown, thus pointing to the ordering of its structure. The crystallographic transition $\gamma \rightarrow \theta$ (900°C) was characterized by dispersing substances, the crystallite sizes again decreased up to 6-7 nm and their value smoothly increased up to the next structural transformations of γ - and θ - Al_2O_3 to α -corundum. The size of the last was increased with increasing annealing temperature above 1300°C .

The behavior of zirconia particles was the same. A smooth growth of grain sizes with increasing annealing temperature was disturbed in the region of structural transformations that were followed by the destruction of the crystallites of the initial phase and by a decrease in their sizes. The X-ray data were well correlated with the electron microscope results for ultrasound-treated fibrous dispersions of partially stabilized zirconia annealed at 450°C . The

microphotographs of the nanostructured powder on a TEM with $\times 120000$ illustrate the particles of alumina three phases: γ , θ , α , their sizes were changed from 4-5 up to 100nm (Fig. 3). The crystallite sizes calculated through the physical broadening of the reflexes of the alumina were equal 4-6 nm for γ – phase and 100-120 – α – corundum. Particles of zirconia tetragonal phase were equal to 6-7 nm and those of the monoclinic phase, 20-23 nm. The dimensionality of ultradispersed particles to be formed in the fibers of metal oxides was studied on an atom-power microscope (APM) allowing the visualizations and quantitative investigations to be possible of the surface topography on a nanometer level. The particle sizes of alumina and zirconia calcined at 600-700⁰C were equal to 3-10 nm. Coincidence of the results obtained by different methods supports the reliability of the experiments conducted.

Elevating of the annealing temperature up to 1100⁰C has induced the micropores and mesopores to disappear. Macropores and closed pores became dominant in the material. The faster the coarsening of pores, the more intensively the material surface is decreased. The value of the specific surface of alumina fibres annealed at 600-700⁰C was 170-200 m²/g and that of the porosity 87-90%. Heating of synthesized fibres up to 1000 - 1200⁰C has decreased the material specific surface because of sintering the refractory oxide particles formed in the fibres. Their sizes were increased up to 100-300 nm. The fibrous alumina-based materials were annealed at a temperature above 1400⁰C and sintered. Their porosity did not exceed 30%, their specific surface decreased up to 5 m²/g, the sizes of grains were equal to 0.1-0.4 μm . In doing so, the material strength can enhance. Thus by varying the heat treatment regime of fibres it appear to possible the control of its porous structure and properties.

Fig. 3: Nanoparticles of alumina phase: γ – (1), $\gamma + \theta$ – (2) and $\alpha + \gamma$ – (3); TEM, $\times 120000$

CONCLUSIONS

The studies made at the Institute of general and Inorganic Chemistry enabled us to establish the mechanism of inorganic fiber formation. At the initial stage a salt solution is adsorbed by polymer fibers. During heat treatment easily volatile components are removed by complex chemical processes, a polymer matrix decomposes, salts dissociate and nano-sized grains of inorganic compounds are formed. Because of the high reactivity the latter contact one to another and form a linear chain structure, whose shape is identical to that of the initial polymer fibers.

Inorganic nanostructural fibres can be used as reinforcing elements, active fillers in composites as well as initial high-dispersed powders to produce porous and dense ceramics. Because of their high reactivity, ceramic materials with a valuable complex of properties can be produced using the classical ceramic technology.

REFERENCES

1. Dujardin, E. and Mann, S., "Bio-Inspired Materials Chemistry", *Advanced Materials*, Vol. 14, No 11, 2002, pp.775-788.
2. Ermolenko, I.N., Ulyanova, T.M., Vityaz, P.A., Fyodorova, I.L., *Fibrous High-Temperature Ceramic Materials*, Nauka i Tekhnika", Minsk, 1991.
3. Gregg, S.J. and Sing, K.S.W. *Adsorption, Surface Area and Porosity*, Academic Press, London, New York 1982.
4. Gusev, A.I. and Rempel, S.V., "X-ray Investigation of Nanostructure of the Degraded Solid Solutions $(\text{ZrC})_{1-x}(\text{NbC})_x$ ", *Journal, Inorganic Materials*, Vol. 39, No 1, 2003, pp. 49-53.
5. Rogovin, Z.A. *Chemistry of Cellulose*, Chemistry, Moscow, 1972.